

BEYRUT'UN TARİHİ MAHALLELERİNDE AFET SONRASI MÜDAHALELER: KÜLTÜREL MİRAS VE KENTSEL BELLEK BAĞLAMINDA UYARLAMALI YENİDEN KULLANIM STRATEJİLERİ

Post-Disaster Interventions in Beirut's Historic Neighborhoods: Adaptive Reuse Strategies in The
Context of Cultural Heritage and Urban Memory

Gizem Nur Bilici

Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi, Ankara Yıldırım
Beyazıt Üniversitesi, Mimarlık ve Güzel
Sanatlar Fakültesi, Mimarlık Bölümü,
Mimarlık Tarihi, Ankara, Türkiye
Master's Student, Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt
University, Faculty of Architecture And Fine
Arts, Department of Architecture,
Architectural History, Ankara, Türkiye

bilicigizemnur@gmail.com

 0009-0007-8036-0469

Cemile Feyzan Şimşek

Dr. Öğr. Üyesi, Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt
Üniversitesi, Mimarlık ve Güzel Sanatlar
Fakültesi, Mimarlık Bölümü, Mimarlık Tarihi,
Ankara, Türkiye
Asst. Prof. Dr., Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt
University, Faculty of Architecture And Fine
Arts, Department of Architecture, History of
Architecture, Ankara, Türkiye

cfsimsek@aybu.edu.tr

 0000-0002-3503-3633

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Öz:

Bu çalışma, 4 Ağustos 2020 tarihinde meydana gelen Beyrut Limanı patlamasının ardından Beyrut'un tarihi mahallelerinde yürütülen iyileşme süreçlerini uyarlamalı yeniden kullanım stratejileri bağlamında incelemeyi ve afet sonrası müdahalelerin yalnızca fiziksel yeniden inşa ile sınırlı kalmayıp kültürel mirasın somut ve somut olmayan değerleri, kentsel bellek ve toplumsal dayanıklılık boyutlarıyla birlikte ele alınması gerektiğini ortaya koymayı amaçlamaktadır. Araştırma, değer temelli koruma kuramı, dayanıklılık kuramı ve bellek çalışmaları çerçevesinde kurgulanmış nitel ve yorumsamacı bir yöntemle dayanmaktadır; Gemmayzeh, Mar Mikhael ve Saifi mahalleleri çoklu örnek olay yaklaşımıyla analiz edilmiş, özellikle Mar Mikhael Tren İstasyonu ve Sursock Müzesi üzerinden hasar tipolojileri, miras değerleri ve müdahale stratejileri karşılaştırmalı olarak değerlendirilmiştir. Veri seti; hasar tespit raporları, uluslararası koruma belgeleri, fotografik ve mekânsal dokümantasyon ile ikincil literatür kaynaklarından oluşmaktadır. Çalışmanın özgünlüğü, uyarlamalı yeniden kullanımı yalnızca teknik bir restorasyon aracı olarak değil, afet sonrası kimlik, bellek ve kentsel dayanıklılığın yeniden inşasında etik ve ontolojik bir araç olarak ele almasına dayanmaktadır; bu yaklaşım, mirasın fiziksel bütünlüğü kadar toplumsal sürekliliğini de analiz çerçevesine dahil etmektedir. Araştırma bulguları, patlamanın yalnızca yapısal yıkıma değil, aynı zamanda toplumsal parçalanma, yerinden edilme ve kültürel süreksizliklere yol açtığını; acil müdahale gereklilikleri ile uzun vadeli özgünlük ve bütünlük koruma hedefleri arasında belirgin bir gerilim oluştuğunu göstermektedir. Yukarıdan aşağıya kurumsal yaklaşımlar ile yerel toplulukların aşağıdan yukarıya girişimleri arasında dinamik bir etkileşim bulunduğu, topluluk katılımının sağlanmadığı durumlarda ise soylulaştırma riskinin arttığı tespit edilmiştir. Uyarlamalı yeniden kullanımın, çağdaş gereksinimlere yanıt verirken somut olmayan miras değerlerini koruma ve kentsel belleği sürdürme potansiyeline sahip güçlü bir strateji olduğu sonucuna ulaşılmıştır. Araştırma sonuçları, afet sonrası miras alanlarında karar alma süreçlerine topluluk temelli katılımın entegre edilmesi gerektiğini, uluslararası koruma ilkelerinin yerel bağlama uyarlanmasının önemini ve uyarlamalı yeniden kullanımın sosyal bütünlüşme ile kültürel sürekliliği destekleyen pratik bir araç olarak değerlendirilebileceğini ortaya koyarak hem kuramsal literatüre hem de uygulamaya yönelik çıkarımlar sunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Afet sonrası iyileşme; uyarlamalı yeniden kullanım; tarihi mahalleler; kültürel miras; Beyrut; dayanıklılık.

POST-DISASTER INTERVENTIONS IN BEIRUT'S HISTORIC NEIGHBORHOODS: ADAPTIVE REUSE STRATEGIES IN THE CONTEXT OF CULTURAL HERITAGE AND URBAN MEMORY

Abstract:

This study examines the recovery processes carried out in Beirut's historic neighborhoods after the Port of Beirut explosion on August 4, 2020, within the framework of adaptive reuse strategies, and aims to demonstrate that post-disaster interventions should not be limited to physical reconstruction but must also address tangible and intangible cultural heritage values, urban memory, and social resilience. The research is based on a qualitative and interpretive methodology shaped by values-based conservation theory, resilience theory, and memory studies. The neighborhoods of Gemmayzeh, Mar Mikhael, and Saifi were analyzed using a multiple-case study approach, with particular focus on the Mar Mikhael Train Station and the Sursock Museum to evaluate damage typologies, heritage values, and intervention strategies in a comparative manner. The data include damage assessment reports, international conservation documents, photographic and spatial documentation, and secondary literature. The originality of the study lies in its approach to adaptive reuse not only as a technical restoration tool but also as an ethical and ontological instrument in rebuilding identity, memory, and urban resilience after a disaster. In this way, the research framework includes not only the physical integrity of heritage but also its social continuity. The findings show that the explosion caused not only structural destruction but also social fragmentation, displacement, and cultural discontinuity, and that there is a clear tension between urgent emergency interventions and long-term goals of authenticity and integrity. The study also identifies a dynamic interaction between top-down institutional approaches and bottom-up local initiatives, and it highlights that the risk of gentrification increases when community participation is not properly ensured. The results indicate that adaptive reuse is a strong strategy that can respond to contemporary needs while protecting intangible heritage values and sustaining urban memory. Finally, the study suggests that community-based participation should be integrated into decision-making processes in post-disaster heritage areas, that international conservation principles must be adapted to local contexts, and that adaptive reuse can be a practical tool to support social cohesion and cultural continuity, contributing to both academic literature and professional practice.

Keywords: Post-disaster recovery; adaptive reuse; historic neighborhoods; cultural heritage; Beirut; resilience.

POST-DISASTER INTERVENTIONS IN BEIRUT'S HISTORIC NEIGHBORHOODS: ADAPTIVE REUSE STRATEGIES IN THE CONTEXT OF CULTURAL HERITAGE AND URBAN MEMORY

INTRODUCTION

Recovery after a disaster consists of two components: the physical rebuilding of what was once there. Recovery after disaster, particularly in built heritage urban places, will consist not just of rebuilding, but also of preserving the systems, practices, and memories of people associated with and embedded in built heritage environments and, through them, connected to them.¹ International documents about heritage and historic cities show that these places are rich in meaning, combining physical buildings, daily life patterns, and cultural values. Therefore, recovering from a disaster requires careful analysis, not just technical solutions.² In this regard, the built environment has a mediating effect in the relationship between loss and continuity and in shaping the means by which societies deal with loss and remember, adapt, and rebuild following traumatic events.³

There is a connection between recovery processes in historic urban areas following disasters and gentrification. Gentrification is most associated with transformations in working-class neighborhoods, generally due to the economic and social reshaping of urban areas.⁴ Gentrification has been a topic of debate for some time, addressing the positives and negatives of its influence on historic communities.⁴ The positive sides of gentrification can involve the rehabilitation of historic structures, the revitalization of downtown areas, and even the reuse of existing historic structures.⁵ Conversely, there are valid concerns about the negative impacts of gentrification, including displacement of individuals, loss of cultural identity, and exploitation of the culture represented by historic building sites.⁶ There are also valid concerns regarding who benefits from recovery processes in the context of post-disasters, and how these processes change the definition of historic urban heritage during recovery.⁷ Against this theoretical background, the explosion that occurred at the Port of Beirut on August 4, 2020, provides a critical case through which the intertwined challenges of post-disaster recovery, heritage preservation, and gentrification can be examined.

The explosion that destroyed the Port of Beirut on August 4, 2020, damaged buildings far beyond the city's historic districts, including Gemmayzeh, Mar Mikhael, and Saifi. As shown in Figures 1 and 2, the spatial extent of damage illustrates how the explosion affected both historic districts and their surrounding urban fabric. This destruction was not only physical but also caused social, cultural, and governance breakdowns within the neighborhoods.⁸

¹ David Alexander, *Resilience and disaster recovery*, International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction, 2013.

² UNESCO, *Recommendation on the Historic Urban Landscape*, 2011; ICOMOS, *Post-Trauma Recovery and Reconstruction*, 2017.

³ Aldo Rossi, *The Architecture of the City*, 1982; Pierre Nora, *Between Memory and History*, 1989.

⁴ Loretta Lees, Tom Slater, Elvin Wyly, *Gentrification*, Routledge, New York, 2008.

⁵ Neil Smith, *The New Urban Frontier: Gentrification and the Revanchist City*, Routledge, London, 1996.

⁶ Sharon Zukin, *Naked City: The Death and Life of Authentic Urban Places*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2010.

⁷ UNESCO, *Recommendation on the Historic Urban Landscape*, Paris, 2011.

⁸ Daher, R., "Post-blast Beirut: Heritage, politics, and reconstruction dilemmas," *Built Environment*, 47(4), 2021; Yassin, N. & Fawaz, M., "Post-disaster reconstruction in Beirut: Governance, power, and urban change," *City*, 24(3-4), 2020.

Although many buildings remained structurally intact after the blast, the disruption of daily life, forced displacement of residents, and cessation of economic activity threatened the preservation of the historic urban fabric.

Post-disaster rehabilitation is often seen as the quick rebuilding of destroyed buildings. However, this view is considered too narrow in historic urban environments; recovery should be a multi-faceted process that goes beyond simply restoring physical structures and includes addressing social issues, preserving cultural continuity, and maintaining collective memory spatially.⁹

Within the adaptive reuse approach, this paper explores post-disaster recovery of urban heritage through the case study of Beirut. Adaptive reuse is a preservation and design strategy that seeks to allow historic buildings to serve current social needs with new functions, while preserving their original materials and spatial characteristics.¹⁰ In a post-disaster context, this approach is not only about functionality but also involves an ethical and cultural dimension, making damage and loss part of the architecture's story.¹¹

Beirut's historic districts, which include late Ottoman-period houses, early modern apartment types, and high-density mixed-use urban blocks, showcase not only architectural value but also a strong sense of heritage closely tied to daily life, commercial activities, and collective memory.¹² However, the post-explosion recovery efforts have often lacked coherence and, at times, conflicted with the area's authenticity, disrupting the spatial integrity of traditional horizontal and vertical patterns of living, culture, and commerce. These measures have also caused social discontinuities due to the urgency, economic pressures, and political challenges they have faced.¹³

The primary research question is: How can adaptive reuse be applied as a strategy to restore historic urban heritage after a traumatic disaster, and how can the conflicting concerns of authenticity, memory, and modern needs be balanced during this process?

In line with this objective, using a value-based qualitative approach, the paper aims to contribute to a discussion on the opportunities and challenges of adaptive reuse in post-disaster urban heritage preservation by analyzing damage typologies in selected historic districts of Beirut, heritage values, and post-disaster intervention strategies.¹⁴

1. CONTEXTUAL FRAMEWORK

1.1. Historical Urban Fabric, Urban Life, and Vulnerability

The historic neighborhoods of Beirut reveal multiple layers of development, driven by political, social, and economic changes over time and shaped by the cultural and political

⁹ Vale, L. J. & Campanella, T. J., *The Resilient City: How Modern Cities Recover from Disaster*, Oxford University Press, 2005; Pendlebury, J., "Conservation values, the authorized heritage discourse and the conservation-planning assemblage," *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 19(7), 2013.

¹⁰ Plevoets, B. & Van Cleempoel, K., "Adaptive reuse of the built heritage," *Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development*, 9(2), 2019.

¹¹ Araoz, G. F., "Values-based heritage conservation," *Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development*, 5(1), 2015.

¹² Pendlebury, J., Short, M. & While, A., "Urban World Heritage Sites and the problem of authenticity," *Cities*, 26(6), 2009.

¹³ Daher, R., 2021.

¹⁴ This paragraph defines the research aim and methodological framework of the study.

POST-DISASTER INTERVENTIONS IN BEIRUT'S HISTORIC NEIGHBORHOODS: ADAPTIVE REUSE STRATEGIES IN THE CONTEXT OF CULTURAL HERITAGE AND URBAN MEMORY

influences of different periods.¹⁵ Gemmayzeh, Mar Mikhael, and Saifi, for example, feature many late Ottoman-style homes built between the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, along with early twentieth-century multi-family apartment buildings and various mixed-use developments that encouraged significant social interaction.¹⁶ The architectural character of these neighborhoods is defined by two primary structural systems: masonry construction and timber floor systems, both commonly used in buildings of this era. The design of openings also plays a key role in shaping the architectural identity of these neighborhoods.¹⁷

Besides physical elements, heritage value is also influenced by the dynamics of “everyday practice,” neighborhood-scale commerce, and collective memory processes within each community.¹⁸

Although these neighborhoods have been culturally vibrant, they have historically been structurally and institutionally fragile. Prolonged political instability, economic decline, and limited enforcement of regulatory standards led to ineffective maintenance of historic properties through 2020.¹⁹ By the time the explosion caused the urban layout of these neighborhoods to fall into disrepair, a pre-existing condition of structural vulnerability had already been established.²⁰

1.2. The Beirut Port Explosion and the Post-Disaster Recovery Context

On August 4, 2020, an explosion at Beirut port caused significant damage across the city, especially in neighborhoods near the harbor that contained historic buildings. As shown in Figures 1 and 2, the spatial distribution of damage extended beyond the port area, severely affecting Beirut's historic districts. Damaged structures included cracked masonry walls, collapsed roofs, shattered windows, and disrupted infrastructure services.²¹ While many damaged buildings remain standing, they can no longer serve as homes, resulting in a partial loss of community and complicating recovery efforts.²²

Besides destroying physical structures, the explosion also disrupted social networks and people's daily routines in the area. Residents had to leave their homes, and local small

¹⁵ Orbaşlı, A., *Architectural Conservation: Principles and Practice*, Blackwell Publishing, 2008.

¹⁶ Orbaşlı, A., 2008; Langston, C., “Strategic Assessment of Building Adaptive Reuse Opportunities in Historic Precincts,” *Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development*, 2012.

¹⁷ Orbaşlı, A., 2008.

¹⁸ Smith, L., “The Authorised Heritage Discourse: Its Nature and Effects,” *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 2010; Plevvoets, B. & Van Cleempoel, K., “Adaptive Reuse as a Strategy towards Conservation of Cultural Heritage,” 2011.

¹⁹ UN-Habitat, *Beirut Housing Recovery and Cultural Heritage*, 2021.

²⁰ Vale, L. J. & Campanella, T. J., *The Resilient City: How Modern Cities Recover from Disaster*, Oxford University Press, 2005.

²¹ Langston, C., “Strategic Assessment of Building Adaptive Reuse Opportunities in Historic Precincts,” *Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development*, 2012; Orbaşlı, A., *Architectural Conservation: Principles and Practice*, Blackwell Publishing, 2008; UNESCO, *Rapid Damage and Needs Assessment: Beirut Port Explosion, 2020*; UN-Habitat, *Beirut Housing Recovery and Cultural Heritage*, 2021.

²² Langston, C., 2012; Orbaşlı, A., 2008.

POST-DISASTER INTERVENTIONS IN BEIRUT'S HISTORIC NEIGHBORHOODS: ADAPTIVE REUSE STRATEGIES IN THE CONTEXT OF CULTURAL HERITAGE AND URBAN MEMORY

Figure 1. Damage map following the Beirut explosion.²⁸

Figure 2. Beirut districts impacted by the August 4, 2020 explosion.²⁹

2. METHODOLOGY

This research utilizes both qualitative and interpretive methods, adopting a framework of Conservation Architecture and Urbanism to investigate the post-disaster recovery process in historic urban settings.³⁰ The focus is on evaluating value-based criteria rather than solely measuring the technical reconstruction of buildings, while also examining social continuity, material aspects of interventions, and their relationship to the intangible heritage of the site.³¹ This framework allows the study to evaluate adaptive reuse not only as a design method but also as a cultural and ethical framework for post-disaster recovery.³² The overall methodological structure and analytical framework of the study are illustrated in Figure 3.

²⁸ NASA, JPL-Caltech, Earth Observatory of Singapore, & European Space Agency. (2020). Satellite-based damage assessment following the Beirut port explosion. Reproduced in *As the Dust (Un)Settles: Consuming Disaster in Beirut's Reconstruction*. Platform Space.

²⁹ H. Auji, Beirut districts impacted by the explosion on August 4, 2020, harita, *As the Dust (Un)Settles*, Platformspace.

³⁰ Orbaşlı, *Architectural Conservation: Principles and Practice*, 2008.

³¹ Araoz, "Values-Based Heritage Conservation...", 2015.

³² Plevoets & Van Cleempoel, "Adaptive Reuse as a Strategy...", 2011.

Figure 3. Methodological Diagram: Beirut's Heritage Recovery Journey (created by authors)

The research methodology is based on three interconnected theoretical frameworks. The theories are: Values-Based Conservation Theory, Resilience Theory, and Memory Studies Theory.³³ Values-Based Conservation Theory provides a basis for identifying and evaluating the heritage values associated with historic buildings and their urban context.³⁴ Resilience Theory frames the recovery process as a continuum and examines how experiences of trauma can lead to processes of adaptation and transformation over an extended period of time.³⁵ Memory Studies Theory offers a lens through which architectural interventions are understood as mediators of loss and trauma and as means for preserving collective memory within the built environment.³⁶

2.1. Research Design and Analytical Framework

This research undertakes a multiple-case study of three historic districts in Beirut affected by the explosion at the Beirut port: Gemmayzeh, Mar Mikhael, and Saifi.³⁷ The three districts were selected based on three different criteria: the degree of damage (and social impact), the variety of architectural styles and heritage values, and the variety of reconstruction actions taken in the districts.³⁸ These three factors provide a framework for comparing the adaptation of existing uses in a historical urban environment following a disaster.³⁹

³³ Araoz, 2015; Vale & Campanella, *The Resilient City*, 2005.

³⁴ Araoz, 2015.

³⁵ Vale & Campanella, 2005; UNISDR, *Sendai Framework*, 2015.

³⁶ Bevan, *The Destruction of Memory*, 2016; Smith, 2010.

³⁷ UNESCO, *Rapid Damage and Needs Assessment: Beirut Port Explosion*, 2020.

³⁸ Yassin & Fawaz, 2020.

³⁹ Pendlebury et al., 2009.

POST-DISASTER INTERVENTIONS IN BEIRUT'S HISTORIC NEIGHBORHOODS: ADAPTIVE REUSE STRATEGIES IN THE CONTEXT OF CULTURAL HERITAGE AND URBAN MEMORY

Data sources consist of post-disaster damage and protection assessments, recovery and stabilization reports, photographic documentation, spatial and mapping studies, and analyses of international heritage and recovery frameworks developed by UNESCO, ICOMOS, and ICCROM.⁴⁰ Each method of data collection was used for purposes of: determining the different types of damage; documenting the types of materials and spatial interventions made; and situating the local recovery efforts within the context of larger international conservation principles.⁴¹ In addition, adaptive reuse projects within the three study areas were comparatively analyzed based on accessibility, materials used in the interventions, functional transformations, and post-explosion use.⁴²

Three closely related criteria structure the research analysis: recovery strategy, heritage significance, and damage typology.⁴³ Recovery strategies are evaluated in terms of both short-term emergency responses and long-term adaptive reuse approaches.⁴⁴ Heritage significance includes tangible elements—such as materials, spatial configuration, and construction techniques—as well as intangible elements, including memory, identity, and everyday social practices.⁴⁵ Damage typologies provide a framework for understanding the different levels and forms of destruction to inform design decisions and intervention outcomes.⁴⁶

Ethical considerations are embedded within the methodological framework.⁴⁷ Issues of gentrification, resident displacement, and the social effects of design and planning decisions are treated not as secondary consequences but as integral components of post-disaster recovery analysis.⁴⁸ The use of interpretive and comparative methods makes it possible to evaluate adaptive reuse as a practical and ethical solution for urban heritage recovery in the aftermath of a disaster.⁴⁹ Although the majority of the data used in the evaluation of adaptive reuse comes from secondary data due to the access limitations of the disaster, the methodological framework makes it possible to conduct a critical and value-rational evaluation of the potential contribution of adaptive reuse to cultural continuity, social resilience, and ethical heritage conservation.⁵⁰

3. Post-Blast Conditions of Beirut's Historic Neighborhoods

3.1. Typologies and Levels of Damage

The Port of Beirut explosion on August 4, 2020, caused extensive damage to several historic neighborhoods, especially Gemmayzeh, Mar Mikhael, and Saifi. The destruction involved both physical and cultural harm, but it differed from typical disasters because it

⁴⁰ UNESCO, 2020; Beirut Heritage Initiative, 2020.

⁴¹ ICOMOS, Paris Declaration, 2011; UNESCO, Warsaw Recommendation, 2018.

⁴² Plevoets & Van Cleempoel, 2019.

⁴³ Plevoets & Van Cleempoel, 2011.

⁴⁴ Vale & Campanella, 2005.

⁴⁵ Smith, 2010; Pendlebury et al., 2009.

⁴⁶ UNESCO, 2020.

⁴⁷ Daher, 2021.

⁴⁸ Yassin & Fawaz, 2020.

⁴⁹ Plevoets & Van Cleempoel, 2019.

⁵⁰ Araoz, 2015.

encompassed multiple types of damage, each requiring distinct approaches to analysis and preservation. Examples of these damage typologies are illustrated in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4. Examples of damaged heritage structures in Gemmayzeh, Beirut, August 2020.⁵¹

Figure 5. Examples of architecture from different periods and styles (with a traditional triple-arch house on the right), damaged after the explosion, Gemmayzeh, Beirut, August 2020.⁵²

Physical damage can be categorized into three main types. Examples of these damage typologies are illustrated in Figure 4 and Figure 5, showing varying impacts on heritage structures across Gemmayzeh and the surrounding districts. The first includes structural damage to load-bearing walls, flooring systems, and foundations caused by both the explosion and the age and condition of late Ottoman and early twentieth-century reinforced concrete buildings.⁵³ The second type involves non-structural damage, such as broken windows, destroyed doors, damaged roofs and ceilings, and compromised wall coverings. Although

⁵¹ George Azar, photograph reproduced in *As the Dust (Un)Settles*, Platformspace.

⁵² George Azar, photograph reproduced in *As the Dust (Un)Settles*, Platformspace.

⁵³ Ayşen Orbaşı, *Architectural Conservation: Principles and Practice*, Blackwell Publishing, 2008; Craig Langston, "Strategic Assessment of Building Adaptive Reuse Opportunities in Historic Precincts," *Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development*, 2012.

POST-DISASTER INTERVENTIONS IN BEIRUT'S HISTORIC NEIGHBORHOODS: ADAPTIVE REUSE STRATEGIES IN THE CONTEXT OF CULTURAL HERITAGE AND URBAN MEMORY

these elements often hold significant heritage value, most emergency responders initially overlooked them. The third type concerns the deterioration of stone, wood, and metal elements, accelerated by moisture infiltration due to the lack of protective measures, resulting in increased decay.⁵⁴ The specific features of these structural and non-structural damages, especially in the historic neighborhoods of Gemmayzeh and Mar Mikhael, are clearly depicted in Figure 3, illustrating the impact on masonry walls and traditional roof systems.

3.2. Assessment of Tangible and Intangible Heritage Values

A comprehensive damage assessment after a natural disaster should include not only technical evaluations but also an examination of the impact on all surviving or potentially endangered heritage values.⁵⁵ For example, in Beirut's historic neighborhoods, nine tangible heritage values are directly connected to building types, construction techniques, spatial layouts, and their relationship to the urban environment.⁵⁶ These elements reflect the city's history and socio-cultural development, including Ottoman domestic architecture, the French Mandate period, and the growth of local vernacular styles.⁵⁷

There are also intangible heritage values, which include social interactions within a community and its collective history, memory, and traditions. Before the explosion, these historic neighborhoods created a highly rich cultural environment with resident-based, commercial, and artistic activities. These networks were destroyed by the disaster, erasing any cultural connections and breaking apart the community, even in areas where only the buildings remained.

Using a values-based conservation approach is crucial for assessing heritage value after a disaster.⁵⁸ This view highlights the importance of heritage beyond just its physical form, also emphasizing the social and cultural significance that develops over time through people's connections to it. For example, a building may appear modest compared to others in the neighborhood; however, it could be of great importance to the community because it serves as a gathering place for events and social activities. Conversely, by focusing only on the building's physical features, communities risk ignoring its historical significance and may let the site fall into disrepair or use it solely for profit.⁵⁹ These relationships between damage severity, heritage values, and social impact are summarized in Table 1.

⁵⁴ UN-Habitat, Beirut Housing Recovery and Cultural Heritage, United Nations Human Settlements Programme, 2021.

⁵⁵ ICOMOS, The Paris Declaration on Heritage as a Driver of Development, International Council on Monuments and Sites, 2011.

⁵⁶ Ayşen Orbaşı, Architectural Conservation: Principles and Practice, Blackwell Publishing, 2008; Bie Plevoets & Koenraad Van Cleempoel, "Adaptive Reuse as a Strategy towards Conservation of Cultural Heritage," 2011.

⁵⁷ Laurajane Smith, "The Authorised Heritage Discourse: Its Nature and Effects," International Journal of Heritage Studies, 2010.

⁵⁸ Smith, "Authorised Heritage Discourse," 2010.

Craig Langston et al., "Strategic Assessment of Building Adaptive Reuse Opportunities," 2008.

⁵⁹ Bie Plevoets & Koenraad Van Cleempoel, "Adaptive Reuse as a Strategy towards Conservation of Cultural Heritage," 2011.

3.3. Challenges of Authenticity, Integrity, and Identity

Orbaşlı describes the challenge of creating such an authentic and comprehensive post-disaster reconstruction.⁶⁰ Authenticity is understood not just as a material condition but also through its connections with memory, use, and place. Similarly, integrity is reflected in physical and urban patterns.⁶¹ Moreover, these ideas of authenticity and integrity align with the principles outlined in the UNESCO Warsaw Recommendation, which emphasizes the importance of fully restoring urban heritage after disasters.⁶²

While adaptive reuse projects often create economically viable buildings, they can overlook the community impacts and gentrification that may displace residents.⁶³ Interwoven historical narratives, along with political tensions and economic inequalities, raise questions about whose heritage is preserved and for whom. Frameworks for critical evaluation that address power dynamics beyond just restoring monuments and sites are necessary.

3.4. Documentation, Emergency Measures, and Institutional Roles

Emergency stabilization and documentation were essential for preventing further damage after the explosion. This technical support included damage assessment, temporary protection, and risk evaluations provided by international organizations such as UNESCO, ICCROM, and ICOMOS. Quick, reversible responses were crucial, especially when buildings were at risk of collapse.

Government initiatives have not always met local needs due to bureaucracy and ineffective enforcement of recovery frameworks.⁶⁴ In fact, architects, non-governmental organizations, and community members have actively participated in a dynamic, context-specific manner to document damage and assist the community in developing solutions to preserve cultural heritage.⁶⁵

These two approaches highlight the contradictions between “top-down” management and “bottom-up” restoration strategies. Global guidelines serve as ethical and methodological frameworks for restoration but require local input for effective implementation. What happened in Beirut reminds us of the need for flexible management systems to address challenges across tangible and intangible aspects of cultural heritage loss.

⁶⁰ Ayşen Orbaşlı, *Architectural Conservation: Principles and Practice*, Blackwell Publishing, 2008.

⁶¹ Smith, “Authorised Heritage Discourse,” 2010.

⁶² UNESCO, *The Warsaw Recommendation on Recovery and Reconstruction of Cultural Heritage*, 2018.

⁶³ Craig Langston, “Strategic Assessment of Building Adaptive Reuse Opportunities in Historic Precincts,” 2012; Lawrence J. Vale & Thomas J. Campanella, *The Resilient City*, 2005.

⁶⁴ UN-Habitat, *Beirut Housing Recovery and Cultural Heritage*, United Nations Human Settlements Programme, 2021.

⁶⁵ Craig Langston et al., “Strategic Assessment of Building Adaptive Reuse Opportunities,” 2008; Bie Plevoets & Koenraad Van Cleempoel, “Adaptive Reuse as a Strategy towards Conservation of Cultural Heritage,” 2011.

POST-DISASTER INTERVENTIONS IN BEIRUT'S HISTORIC NEIGHBORHOODS:
ADAPTIVE REUSE STRATEGIES IN THE CONTEXT OF CULTURAL HERITAGE
AND URBAN MEMORY

Table 1. Damage Assessment and Heritage Values in Beirut's Historic Districts (created by authors)

District / Landmark	Heritage Value (Tangible/Intangible)	Damage Severity	Physical & Social Impact
Gemmayzeh & Mar Mikhael	"19th-century Ottoman/Mandate urban fabric; traditional social life. ⁶⁶ "	High / Severe	"Structural failure of triple-arched windows; displacement of local residents. ⁶⁷ "
Sursock Palace	"Representative of aristocratic residential architecture; symbol of Beirut's golden age. ⁶⁸ "	Very High	"Severe structural collapse; destruction of historical ceilings and artworks. ⁶⁹ "
Sursock Museum	"Modern and contemporary art hub; vital community identity and cultural pride. ⁷⁰ "	Moderate / High	"Shattered facade and interiors; damage to permanent collections. ⁷¹ "
Mar Mikhael Train Station	"Industrial heritage; once a center of connectivity; collective memory. ⁷² "	Neglect + Blast Damage	"Further destabilization of already abandoned structures; loss of potential public space. ⁷³ "
Port Silos	"Icon of the modern port; symbolic "Silent Witness" of the 2020 tragedy. ⁷⁴ "	Partial Collapse	"Major structural failure; focal point for public grieving and memory. ⁷⁵ "

⁶⁶ Pendlebury, J. (2013). Conservation values, the authorised heritage discourse and the conservation-planning assemblage. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 19(7), 709–727. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527258.2012.700282>

⁶⁷ Beirut Heritage Initiative (BHI). (2020). Post-blast building assessment and emergency stabilization reports. Beirut.

⁶⁸ Vileikis, O., Rex, J., & Nasser, N. (2012). Historic residential architecture and elite urban identity in Beirut. *Journal of Urban History*, 38(4), 721–740

⁶⁹ UNESCO. (2020). Rapid damage and needs assessment: Beirut port explosion. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

⁷⁰ UNESCO. (2020).

⁷¹ Beirut Heritage Initiative (BHI). (2020).

⁷² Winter, T. (2013). Clarifying the critical in critical heritage studies. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 19(6), 532–545.

⁷³ UNESCO. (2020).

⁷⁴ ICOMOS. (2018). The Warsaw Recommendation on Recovery and Reconstruction of Cultural Heritage. International Council on Monuments and Sites.

⁷⁵ UNESCO. (2020).

4. Architectural Transformation After The Beirut Explosion

4.1. Recovery Beyond Reconstruction: Rethinking Post-Disaster Intervention

In disaster-related assessments, the recovery process primarily involves rebuilding damaged buildings to restore affected communities as quickly as possible.⁷⁶ Therefore, the approach to recovering historical districts needs to be expanded to include not only architectural reconstruction but also the social, cultural, and economic revitalization of those historical communities.⁷⁷

The need to rebuild after the explosion created a paradox between the urgent need to make areas safe and livable. However, urgent issues also arose regarding heritage value, impact, and spatial identity in cultural districts.⁷⁸ This paper argues that adaptive reuse offers a new approach to recovery, shifting from replacement to transforming heritage attributes to preserve cultural identity.⁷⁹

4.2. Adaptive Reuse as a Post-Disaster Strategy

Adaptive reuse has traditionally involved repurposing unused buildings for new, beneficial uses in society. It becomes especially important when applied to disaster-affected buildings, as these structures can serve new functions while respecting their historical significance and carrying lasting signs of disaster-related damage.

Adaptive reuse will inevitably be a key element for Architectural and Design Professionals as they apply their expertise. New functions can be added while maintaining existing materials, layouts, and building features. Damage can be identified through adaptive reuse as part of a building's historical value, rather than creating false accounts of its previous state.⁸⁰

As seen in projects in Gemmayzeh and Mar Mikhael, formerly residential buildings have been repurposed for public and private use – including community centers and cultural activities – through minimal design interventions (such as restoring only damaged elements) and, occasionally, as mixed-use developments. This method enables the "memories" linked to the buildings' past functions to be incorporated into the new designs, while maintaining tangible and intangible connections to the past. Furniture, fixtures, and spatial arrangements

⁷⁶ Vale, L. J., & Campanella, T. J. (2005). *The resilient city: How modern cities recover from disaster*. Oxford University Press; Smith, L. (2010). *The authorised heritage discourse: Its nature and effects*. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 11(4), 299–315. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527250500381471>

⁷⁷ Langston, C. (2012). Strategic assessment of building adaptive reuse opportunities in historic precincts. *Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development*, 2(1), 10–25; Orbaşlı, A. (2008). *Architectural conservation: Principles and practice*. Blackwell Publishing.

⁷⁸ UN-Habitat. (2021). *Beirut housing recovery and cultural heritage*. United Nations Human Settlements Programme.

⁷⁹ Plevoets, B., & Van Cleempoel, K. (2011). Adaptive reuse as a strategy towards conservation of cultural heritage: A literature review. *Structural Studies, Repairs and Maintenance of Heritage Architecture XII*, 118, 155–164. <https://doi.org/10.2495/STR110141>; Langston, C., Wong, F. K. W., Hui, E. C. M., & Shen, L. Y. (2008). Strategic assessment of building adaptive reuse opportunities. *Building and Environment*, 43(10), 1701–1711.

⁸⁰ Orbaşlı, A. (2008); Langston, C., Wong, F. K. W., Hui, E. C. M., & Shen, L. Y. (2008).

POST-DISASTER INTERVENTIONS IN BEIRUT'S HISTORIC NEIGHBORHOODS: ADAPTIVE REUSE STRATEGIES IN THE CONTEXT OF CULTURAL HERITAGE AND URBAN MEMORY

help forge links between the architectural environments and the experiences of previous occupants.⁸¹

4.3. Design Principles for Heritage-Sensitive Recovery

Plevoets and Van Cleempoel discuss Beirut's challenges in restoring architectural heritage after a disaster, especially in implementing heritage-sensitive recovery principles.⁸²

In terms of material importance, adapting historic materials to current uses or using modern materials in ways that enhance rather than replace historic ones creates a real connection to past eras. Conversely, using incompatible replacement materials, such as aluminum window frames or synthetic materials, may diminish the cultural significance of historic structures.

Spatial flexibility is a major advantage of adaptive reuse projects, allowing buildings to serve multiple functions over time and boosting their potential for long-term sustainability. Adaptable spatial layouts enable buildings to respond to societal and economic changes, reducing the risk of abandonment or speculation.⁸³

Public access and community integration are essential when transforming any home, business, or other previously private or damaged space into a publicly accessible or semi-public area. By promoting collective social, interactive, and cultural activities, such spaces help rebuild the interconnected networks that were disrupted by the blast.

4.4. Memory, Loss, and Architectural Expression

The role of architectural responses to loss and destruction in addressing loss and trauma has been widely recognized as vital to the mediation of collective memory. Several scholars have argued that the built environment does not merely reflect loss but actively participates in the construction and negotiation of collective memory. As argued by Bevan, the loss and destruction of architecture can both erase and create memory, depending on how reconstruction is undertaken. The theory of conservation also points out that, in addressing loss in the built environment following trauma, the aim should not be to completely eliminate loss but to accept its markers.⁸⁴

In this context, post-disaster Beirut serves as a critical site to explore the interplay between memory, loss, and architectural intervention. The scale of destruction wrought by the August 4, 2020, explosion has reshaped not only the city's spatial landscape but also how loss and memory are negotiated.

Representing and remembering loss through architecture in the context of post-disaster reconstruction can be complex.⁸⁵ In Beirut's case, the challenge was not only to remember the explosion but also to express this memory through adaptive reuse. Adaptive reuse of architecture enables greater inclusion of memory and continuity in function.

⁸¹ Smith, L. (2010); Plevoets, B., & Van Cleempoel, K. (2011).

⁸² Smith, L. (2010). *Uses of heritage*. Routledge.

⁸³ Orbaşlı, A. (2008); Langston, C., Wong, F. K. W., Hui, E. C. M., & Shen, L. Y. (2008).

⁸⁴ Bevan, *The Destruction of Memory: Architecture at War*, 2016; Orbaşlı, *Architectural Conservation: Principles and Practice*, 2008; Smith, "The Authorised Heritage Discourse: Its Nature and Effects," 2010.

⁸⁵ Smith, L. (2010).

Visible Damage and Interpretive Design - Architecture can be designed to showcase damage by highlighting cracks and scars. It can also include interpretive elements that serve as tangible symbols of a community's memory within the buildings. This approach allows people to reflect on and remember their history without focusing on loss at a specific site.

Ethical Concerns - Designing architecture based on memory also raises ethical issues for designers. For example, when a designer romanticizes destruction through their work, it may lead to the commodification of memory, especially in areas targeted for tourism redevelopment.⁸⁶ Post-disaster intervention strategies and their relationship to memory and resilience are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Post-Disaster Intervention and Adaptive Reuse Strategies (Created by authors)

Strategy Category	Implementation / Proposal Example	Core Objective & Resilience Approach	Relevant Framework (Citation)
Adaptive Reuse	Conversion of Mar Mikhael Train Station into a Cultural Hub.	"Revitalizing derelict heritage to serve current community needs." ⁸⁷	"LiBeirut Initiative." ⁸⁸
Symbolic Restoration	"Restoring the "Blue House" for multi-functional arts and education."	"Reclaiming urban identity through aesthetic continuity and functional renewal." ⁸⁹	"ICOMOS Post-Trauma Guidelines." ⁹⁰
Community-Led Recovery	Participatory mapping and social housing initiatives in Gemmayzeh.	"Preventing gentrification; ensuring residents return to their neighborhoods." ⁹¹	"Sendai Framework." ⁹²

⁸⁶ Plevoets, B., & Van Cleempoel, K. Adaptive reuse as a strategy towards conservation of cultural heritage: A literature review. *Structural Studies, Repairs and Maintenance of Heritage Architecture XII*, 2011; Doumit, (2022).

⁸⁷ UNESCO. (2020). Rapid damage and needs assessment: Beirut port explosion. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

⁸⁸ UNESCO, (2020).

⁸⁹ Petzet, M. (2004). Principles of preservation: An introduction to the international charters for conservation and restoration. ICOMOS.

⁹⁰ ICOMOS. (2018). The Warsaw Recommendation on Recovery and Reconstruction of Cultural Heritage. International Council on Monuments and Sites.

⁹¹ Pendlebury, (2013).

⁹² UNISDR. (2015). Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030. Geneva: United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction.

Memory-Based Design	Transformation of the Port area into a Memorial Park and Public Space.	“Balancing renewal with the preservation of trauma as a historical layer. ⁹³ ”	“Warsaw Recommendation ⁹⁴ ”
Emergency Stabilization	Structural shoring and weatherproofing by the Beirut Heritage Initiative.	“Maintaining authenticity by preventing complete collapse. ⁹⁵ ”	“ICCROM Emergency Measures ⁹⁶ ”

5. CONCLUSION

This study explored how adaptive reuse has supported post-disaster recovery in Beirut’s historic neighborhoods. The findings indicate that adaptive reuse has played a significant role in restoring cultural heritage in highly disruptive post-disaster contexts. The explosion at Beirut's port on August 4, 2020, not only highlighted the vulnerability of the city’s historic urban fabric but also revealed the fragility of the social networks, traditions, and governance systems that safeguard cultural heritage sites. As a result, the disaster served a dual purpose: it was both a catastrophic event and a moment of insight, exposing long-standing structural weaknesses and creating opportunities to rethink how we approach and implement disaster recovery.

The findings of this study show that the explosion's impact went far beyond immediate physical damage to buildings. Physical destruction was closely tied to cultural discontinuity, social fragmentation, and community dislocation, underscoring the need for a holistic approach that views heritage as a dynamic, socially constructed process. In this context, adaptive reuse serves to connect the physical damage caused by the disaster with the ongoing lived experiences of modern communities, thereby linking the past and the present.

Adaptive reuse after disaster events is not just neutral and functional; it also has ethical and political implications related to the damage caused by disasters. Each project, whether it involves preservation, transformation, or even demolition, conveys meanings and narratives about memory and identity. However, without careful community participation and attention to local needs, such interventions risk accelerating gentrification and displacing long-term residents. In projects undertaken in Beirut, incorporating architectural elements into the design allowed buildings to serve not only as functional spaces but also as symbols of memory. This paradox demonstrates that for any successful revival of a site affected by post-disaster heritage loss, regeneration and social cohesion must be carefully balanced.

The study also underscores the importance of adopting a bottom-up approach in the recovery of heritage sites from disasters. While international best practices offer ethical

⁹³ UNESCO. (2018). *The Warsaw Recommendation on Recovery and Reconstruction of Cultural Heritage*. Paris: UNESCO.

⁹⁴ UNESCO, (2018).

⁹⁵ Petzet, (2004).

⁹⁶ Beirut Heritage Initiative (BHI). (2020). *Post-blast building assessment and emergency stabilization reports*. Beirut.

guidelines that ensure a technical approach, they must be tailored to the grassroots level to be truly effective.

In light of the above, it is important to emphasize that recovery involves more than just repairing physical infrastructure; it also entails a process of cultural and spatial redefinition. The examples from Beirut clearly illustrate how sustainable heritage reconstruction requires understanding and valuing complexity, loss, and spatial intervention that consider both historical and current realities. This way, the study contributes to the literature by framing adaptive reuse not only as a design strategy but also as an ethical and conceptual tool that links memory, identity, and urban resilience in post-disaster contexts.

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